

MULTI-MODE VIBRATION DETECTION FOR DELAMINATION OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE PLATE

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ABSTRACT

The vibration-based structural health monitoring (SHM) has been widely studied in the damage identification field. Due to the damage, the physical parameters of the structure would be changed, which may affect the dynamic response of the structures, such as natural frequencies, damping ratio, phase, mode shape, etc. And the parameter changes could be used to predict and estimate the damage information. At present, most SHM studies focused on the frequency changing of composite plate, but the damping as a more sensitive parameter has not been adequately utilized. In this paper, the multi-mode vibration detection method is proposed, which combined with the natural frequencies and damping of the composite plate to identify the delamination information. Through simulating the effect of damages on composite plate with finite element software COMSOL, the one-to-one mapping relationship between multiple modes natural frequencies and the size and in-plane location were obtained, and the mode 3rd and mode 5th were selected to predict the delamination. In the experiment, carbon fibre composite plates with artificial delamination were fabricated. The vibration mode signals were detected by piezoelectric materials and analysed by FFT and Hilbert transform to calculate the natural frequencies and damping ratios of composite plates. By the inverse problem method, the predicted values of X-location were consistent with the actual location of delamination in experiment, which the error was less than 3%.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, composite materials have been used increasingly in many engineering applications to make composite laminated structures due to their attractive mechanical performances and their stable physical and chemical properties such as higher strength- weight ratio, great reproductivity and resilience handling [1]. However, structural failure could occur throughout the lifecycle of the composite materials, which often lead to catastrophic consequences, especially in the aerospace, aircraft and other industrial fields. Failure analysis of laminated composite structures has gradually increasing interest in recent year. Typical damage types of composite structures are debonding, interface cracking, matrix cracking and delamination in cross-ply laminate. As the most common failure modes in composite structures, delamination is represented by the separation of two adjacent interfaces of laminate structures [2]. Therefore, for maintaining the integrity and safety of composite structure, the damage detection, especially real-time, becomes a necessary part of industrial manufacturing and on-line monitoring [3].

For structural health monitoring (SHM), the large number of detection techniques have been achieved, such as modal strain energy, transmissibility, lamb waves, ultrasonic inspection and infrared thermography. However, they were somehow challenging to carry out, and some of them were impractical in many cases and the detectable damage were immensely limited [4, 5]. Fortunately, the vibration-based damage detection techniques based on smart materials offered an effective method to damage detection online. This method could monitor the generation and crack propagation of delamination in real time, and identify the potential damages in composite structures early, which would help to reduce risk, save costs, and enhance the safety factor of composite structures.

In the literature, more effective methods of damage detection using vibration-based method have been considered and proposed. Y. Zou et al. utilised the modal-based (MB) [6] methods to simulate the damage by finite element analysis, and compared with experimental data and analytical data to determine damage location and extent. Results showed that various response parameters of the structure such as frequency response, time response and impedance response could be related to the information of delamination. However, the MB methods were dependent heavily on the accuracy of the structural model and these methods have difficulties in applying to complex structures. Zhifang et al. proposed to use a graphical method to solve the inverse problem of identifying damage by the frequency-based vibration monitoring system [7, 8]. Results of the graphical method with simulated mode shapes shown that could identify the physical parameters accuracy, including delamination interface in z-axis, location in plane and size. Alamdari et al developed a more robust frequency response function (FRF), based on damage identification method, to detect and orient structural damage in different conditions. The frequency response-based damage identification methods were superior to conventional model-based approaches as they have a lower error rate in the wide range of frequency domain.

For vibration-based SHM, most researchers focused on the frequency shift to predict the damage information, but it was not sufficiently accurate only based on frequency domain. Damping, mass and other factors might affect the frequency changing of structures, resulting in error superimposed. Therefore, researchers started to explore how to obtain damage information through other response parameters or combination parameters. Chen Yang et al. have numerically and experimentally studied a delamination detection method using additional mass loading and modal frequencies. The study expressed that the interaction between local inertia and delamination affected the vibration characteristics of composite laminated beams for delamination located at different depths. According to Keye, Rose, and Sachau, the modal damping factors might be a more sensitive parameter to damage in delaminated composite structures than natural frequencies [7, 8]. The results showed that due to the better damping characteristics, the lighter materials were more sensitive to damage compared to the heavy materials. It was concluded that damping shows more sensitivity to damage than changes in stiffness. Therefore, it was suggested the use of damping as a damage indicator for SHM purposes in composite materials.

This paper aims to address research as mentioned earlier gap through combining with frequency and damping of composite structures to identify the damage information by multi-mode vibrating [12, 13]. The principle of the multi-mode vibration detection method was using the sensitivity of various modes for the damage and combining the frequency and damping shifting to estimate the size and location of delamination. Compared with other dynamic parameters, the damping ratio was more sensitivity to detect the damage and could accurately sense the changing in stiffness due to the presence of defects [14]. The contents of this paper were as follow. Sec. 2 presented the finite element simulation model of carbon fibre composite plate. Sec. 3 explained the experimental detection method of composite plates, these included the fabrication of the carbon fibre composite plate and the experimental set-up and signal processing. In Sec.4, the results of finite element model and the experimental validation of delamination composite plate have been shown.

2 THE MODEL OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE PLATE

As above mentioned, the function relationship between frequency shifts and damage parameters could be used for delamination detection. In this paper, the FE model for composite structures has been built to simulate the natural frequencies of composite plates [15]. The main purpose of finite element simulation work was to establish the one-to-one mapping relationship between the natural frequencies of various vibration modes of composite plate and the size and in plane location of delamination, to explore the frequency sensitivity of multiple vibration modes, and to select the optimum modes that could be utilised for delamination detection.

Three dimensional (3D) finite element model was performed by the commercial software COMSOL to predict the delamination numerically [16]. The composite structures consisted of 4 layers of carbon fibre prepreg sheets stacked together, each of which has different Young modulus, Poisson ratio, fibre orientation and density. Different fibre orientations determine different material properties, which could be set precisely in COMSOL[15,17,18]. The centre of the composite plate was set to a fixed

constraint, and the piezoelectric material was added to the uppermost layer of the composite plates, as shown in figure 1. All delaminations were inserted between the interface 1 and interface 2. Along the periphery of the square delamination, the nodes of the interfaces were separated from each other, but the nodes of undelaminated segment were merged with each other, the four layer laminate composite plate could be regarded as a whole.

Figure 1. Delamination defect and sensors location with layer configuration.

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

To verify the results of finite element simulation, eight composite plates with delamination were fabricated, and a vibration test platform was built to measure the vibrating frequencies and damping ratio of composite plates.

3.1 Fabrication of carbon fibre composite plate

The carbon fibre-reinforced composite plates were fabricated with prepreg tapes by cutting, stacking processes (hand lay-up), vacuum bag assembly, curing in the high temperature chamber and post-curing [19, 20]. A pre-determined PTFE was manually inserted between interface 1 and interface 2 to simulation defects. The size and in-plane location of delaminations were listed in Table 1 [7]. A circular hole with a diameter of 5mm was drilled in the centre of composite plate. The frequency and damping ratios were explored by changing the size and location (X and Y) in composite structures. After curing in the high-temperature vacuum system, the composite plates were cut into the designed size to ensure each composite plate had the same processing environment. The delamination in carbon fibre composite plates 1 to 4 located at the left ($X=15\text{mm}$, $Y=15\text{mm}$) and had a different size, whose defect area ratio increased from 1.384% to 5.536%, these plates were used to identify the dimensions of the damage. In the plates 5 to 8, the delamination had the same size, but their locations were different, these plates were used to identify the location of the damage. Compared with other composite plates, plate 1 and 5 have no defects, and they would be used as reference values for natural frequencies and damping ratios.

Plate Number	Laminate interface	Damage size (mm \times mm)	X axis location (mm)	Y axis location (mm)
1	Intact	n/a	n/a	n/a
2	1~2	20 \times 20	15	15
3	1~2	30 \times 30	15	15
4	1~2	40 \times 40	15	15
5	Intact	n/a	n/a	n/a
6	1~2	30 \times 30	15	15
7	1~2	30 \times 30	15	125
8	1~2	30 \times 30	125	15

Table 1. The interface, size and in-plane localization of artificial inserted delamination.

3.2 Experimental set-up and signal processing

The sinusoidal signal generated by the signal generator was transmitted through the power amplifier to the vibration shaker to achieve its periodic vibration. The composite plate was placed on the vibration shaker, and the centre of the plate was fixed by a screw, just like the fixed constraints in the COMSOL. The piezo film sensors were attached to the top surface of composite plate to detect the signal of multiple vibration modes, shown in the figure1 [21, 22]. Unlike the PZT Ceramics, the piezo films were extremely flexible, which allowed it to be easily bent, twisted, and attached to structural surfaces, making it more convenient for sensing applications. According to piezoelectric effect, the sensors converted the mechanical strain into voltage when attached to the surface of mechanical structure. The oscilloscope recorded the voltage signal generated by the piezo film sensor under the strain of tension and compression. The test system as shown in Figure 2. The signals of continuous vibrating and ring-down vibrating of composite plate were measured, and the frequencies and damping ratios information were obtained by Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) and Hilbert Transform respectively, shown in the Fig.2.

Figure 2. Experimental set-up of the vibration test platform.

In figure 3 (a), the composite plates were continuously vibrating under the periodic loads during $t=0.7\sim 0.824s$. When $t=0.824s$, the excitation force was turned off. The magnitude of vibrating signal was decreased exponentially due to the damping ratio. That was ring-down measurement. Ring-down reflected the energy decay of the structure in a period. The frequencies of vibration mode of composite plate could be obtained after Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT), shown in figure 3 (c). The two peaks in frequency domain correspond to mode 3 and mode 5 respectively, which were very close to the simulation results in COMSOL. The vibrating frequencies of mode 3rd and mode 5th were 220.95Hz, 379.33Hz. At the same time, the ring-down data were transformed into Hilbert transform, and the real part $v(t)$ and imaginary part $\tilde{v}(t)$ of the signal was obtained in figure 3 (b). By using formula (1) and exponential fitting, the damping ratio of composite plate could be calculated as shown in figure 2 (d).

$$|V|(t) = \sqrt{v^2(t) + \tilde{v}^2(t)} \quad (1)$$

In order to obtain the natural frequency of each composite plate accurately, it was necessary to eliminate the influence of damping and mass. Through formula (2), the natural frequency of each composite plate could be calculated.

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{(1 + \xi^2)\omega_d^2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3. The measured ring-down response of composite plate and 3rd, 4th mode response by FFT and Hilbert transform.

4 RESULTS

4.1 The results of FE simulation

By changing the size and position of the delamination of the defects on the composite plates, the natural frequency shifts were simulated. The increasing of stiffness would increase the natural frequencies of the structure, monitoring the natural frequencies changing might help to record the incidence of damage. As shown in Figure 4(a), the maximum frequency shift increased with the increase of the mode number of composite plate, which meant the frequency sensitivity of the higher mode increased accordingly. We preferred to choose the higher mode for delamination detection, but in the practice case, higher mode would be more difficult to be excited. The linear relationship shown in figure 4(b, c) could be used to reversely identify the size and location of delamination, which lay the foundation for later experimental verification.

Figure 4. The relationship between the natural frequency of composite plate mode and the size of delamination

4.2 Identification of delamination dimensions

The damping ratio was measured using the ring-down method in various artificial delamination composite plate (plate 1 to 4) for obtaining functional relationship between the damage size and damping ratio. With the increasing the defect area ratio of delamination from 0% to 5.54%, the inserted PTFE made the damping ratio kept growing from 0.0095 to 0.021, as shown in figure 5. The fitting function relationship between defect area ratio A_d and damping ratio ξ could be expressed as follow:

$$\xi = 0.0096 + 0.3225 \cdot A_d - 2.158 \cdot A_d^2 \quad (3)$$

The reason was that the local stiffness of composite plates decreased due to the existence of delamination, and there was a gap between the layers of laminate materials. The energy dissipation of composite plates increased in one cycle, which made the damping ratio of composite structure increased. The parabolic mapping relationship could be applied to inversely predict the size of the defect under the assumption that the damping ratio of single delamination has been measured.

For composite materials, damping appears to be a suitable candidate to be used as a damage sensitive feature. This was because there was a correlation between damping and energy dissipated on the composite material during vibration. It was noteworthy to mention that the natural frequencies could also provide information about the presence of damage, as this was usually related to a reduction in stiffness, but it was the combination of different parameters what usually made a more robust method. Vibration-based delamination detection could be regarded as an optimization problem in which the main purpose was to determine and select the optimal physical parameters so as to obtain the system output which were sufficiently close to the real structure. Therefore, we need to trade-off each response parameter to ensure that the accuracy of each parameter has optimum value.

Figure 5. The damping ratio for various size of damage and parabolic fitting for the data.

4.3 Identification of in-plane location of delamination

The natural frequency shift was compared based on the delamination predicted at the individual vibration mode, which was primarily used to locate the in-plane delamination. For each in-plane position, the frequency shifts ratio in each mode could be plotted against the delamination location “x” and “y” to provide a 3D surface in figure 6 (a). Figure 6 (b) was the projection of 3D plot in XZ plane. Changing the delamination location in composite plate along the X and Y axis with step of 10mm, and simulating the composite plate with each delamination position, the corresponding natural frequencies of mode 3rd were obtained. In figure 6 (b), the natural frequencies of composite plate decreased with the increase of the delamination position along X axis with a parabolic relationship. In this work, the maximum effective detection area which could be applied to detect accounted for 25% of total area of each composite plate. The experimental validation value was plotted by the red space in the 3D surface, shown in figure 6 (a). By the inverse problem method, the predicted values of x-location is consistent with the actual location of delamination in experiment, which the error was less than 3%, shown in figure 6 (b).

Figure 6. The relationship between 3rd mode frequency shifts ratio and X, Y location of damage.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the multi-mode vibration detection method has been proposed to identify the delamination of composite structure. A finite element simulation software was employed to build the one-to-one mapping relationship between the natural frequencies of variation modes and the configuration of different pre-designed damages. For experimental validations, carbon fibre composite plates were fabricated with artificially inserted delamination by polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). Experimental testing method was achieved based on the smart materials to detect the multi-mode vibration signal and calculate the information of practical frequency and damping ratio. Furthermore, the size of delamination was accurately estimated using the damping ratio, and the location was inversely predicted using the one-to-one frequency mapping relationship. At present, the identification and prediction of delamination were based on single damage. Future work will consider realizing the identification of multiple damage. The vibration sensors array method and modal coordinate method will be carried out to improve the accuracy of delamination detection.

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